

Regulation of APX and GPX gene expression during natural and drought-induced leaf senescence in wheat

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ABSTRACT

Bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is the main strategic food crop worldwide. Population growth increases global demand for wheat. Drought stress affects plant development, productivity, and growth, thereby activating drought-resistance strategies. Drought is one of the most important abiotic stresses influencing crop growth and development. Leaf senescence comprises numerous interconnected processes, integrating environmental signals with age-related cues and coordinating nutrient remobilization through source-to-sink transport. In crops, senescence has long been considered an essential stage for productivity and quality. However, the functional characterization of candidate genes regulating wheat senescence is still limited. Loss of antioxidant capacity during aging has been reported in various plants. To detoxify reactive oxygen species (ROS), plants have evolved antioxidant enzymes and compounds. Ascorbate peroxidase (APX, EC 1.11.1.11) is one of the key enzymes detoxifying H₂O₂, and distinct isoforms have specific physiological roles. The aim of this study was to investigate the molecular and biochemical mechanisms of drought-induced leaf senescence in different wheat genotypes, with a particular focus on the expression of *APX* and *GPX* genes. Bread wheat genotypes included the tolerant Gyrmzy gul 1 and the sensitive Tale 38, while durum wheat genotypes included the tolerant Vugar and the sensitive Tartar. Flag leaves were collected at 7, 14, 21, 28, and 35 days after anthesis (DAA), frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored at -80°C. RNA extraction was carried out using the Monarch Total RNA Miniprep Kit, cDNA was synthesized with the LunaScript RT SuperMix Kit, and gene expression was analyzed via qRT-PCR using *Elf1-α* as a reference. Expression levels were calculated using the 2^{-ΔΔCt} method. *APX* expression increased during the late stages of natural senescence; however, under drought-induced senescence this increase occurred earlier in tolerant genotypes (day 21 in Vugar, day 14 in Gyrmzy gul 1). In sensitive genotypes (Tartar and Tale 38), peaks occurred at 21 DAA. *GPX* expression, similar to *APX*, peaked at 28 DAA in all genotypes under natural senescence. Under drought-induced senescence, it peaked at 14 DAA in tolerant genotypes and at 28 DAA in sensitive ones. These findings provide a valuable scientific basis for wheat breeding programs aimed at identifying drought-tolerant genotypes during senescence and for the development of stress-resistant plant varieties through genetic modification. Targeted manipulation of *APX* and *GPX* gene expression may facilitate the development of new high-yielding and stress-tolerant wheat lines in the future.

Keywords: Leaf senescence, APX, GPX, gene expression